

METHOD FOR DETERMINING THE MOBILITY OF NERVOUS PROCESSES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7962498>

The emergence of the possibility of multiple registration of psychophysiological indicators led to the understanding of functional states as a complex of behavioral manifestations that accompany various aspects of human activity and behavior [Grimak, 1987].

Thus, it is believed that in the process of playing sports, athletes increase the strength and mobility of nervous processes in the cerebral cortex, improve the balance of the processes of excitation and inhibition, and increase the plasticity of the central nervous system [Petrovsky, 1979].

Also, in the body there is a large number of conditioned reflex connections between the cerebral cortex, internal organs and the motor apparatus, therefore, the determination of these properties (which are also indicators of the functional state of the nervous system) in people professionally involved in sports is an interesting and urgent task.

The nervous system controls the diverse and complex activities of all organs and systems of the human body, regulates all processes occurring in it. It connects the body with changing environmental conditions.

Without the participation of the nervous system, primarily the central nervous system, not a single physical exercise can be performed.

Thanks to the nervous system, all organs work in concert [Filin, 2008].

I.P Pavlov (1910) found that the adaptation of the organism to the environment occurs with the help of reflexes, i.e., reactions (responses) of the organism to stimuli coming from the external environment. Physical exercise is one such powerful stimulus. In the process of playing sports in the body, a large number of conditioned reflex connections arise between the cerebral cortex, internal organs and the motor apparatus. Sports activities have a beneficial effect on the central nervous system and improve its activity [Anokhin, 1968].

The conditioned reflex, which was developed during the training, helps to improve the functioning of the body. Each workout adds something new to what is already there [Petrovsky, 1979].

When an athlete learns any new movement, at first it turns out to be clumsy for him, but in the process of constant training, the movement becomes more rational, more dexterous. In the brain, new connections arise between nerve cells that control the work of the muscles involved in the new movement.

The mobility of the nervous processes was determined using the "Reaction of Discrimination" (RR) technique. Unlike a simple reaction, a discrimination reaction is carried out to one specific stimulus from several different stimuli. Therefore, the process of processing sensory information by the central nervous system occurs not only according to the principle of the presence or absence of a signal, but also according to the principle of distinguishing signals, selecting signals of a certain color from their total number and forming a reaction to a given type of signal. Due to the more complex process of processing sensory information by the central nervous system, the rate of the discrimination reaction is lower than the rate of a simple reaction [Mantrova, 2007].

The analysis of the obtained results is carried out on the basis of the mean value and standard deviation; in the absence of a normal distribution, based on the median and percentiles. In addition, the number of errors and the coefficient of accuracy must be taken into account. The value of the average value indicates the mobility of nervous processes, the standard deviation indicates balance, the dynamics of reaction time values indicates the strength of nervous processes.

References:

1. Anokhin, P.K. Biology and neurophysiology of the conditioned reflex [text] / P.K. Anokhin. – M.: Medicine, 1968. – 548 p.
2. Grimak, L.P. Reserves of the human psyche. Introduction to the psychology of activity [Text] / L.P. Grimak. - M., 1987. - 319 p.
3. Mantrova, I.N. Methodological guide to psychophysiological and psychological diagnostics [Text] / I.N. Mantrova - Ivanovo, 2007. - 211 p.
4. Petrovsky, B.V. Popular medical encyclopedia [Text] / B.V. Petrovsky - M.: Soviet Encyclopedia 1979. - 704 p.
5. Filin, S. P. Concepts of modern natural science. Lecture notes [Text] / S.P. Filin - M.: Eksmo, 2008. - 160 p.